

RDA Minimal Metadata for Learning Resources *Professional and Informal Education* Examples
October 2021

	A	B	C	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	Name			Professional development			Informal education		
2	Definition	Type	Allowed values	Example	Other constraints	Allowed values	Example	Other constraints	
3	Title	The human readable name of the resource.	TEXT (1000)	Free text	Data Management Expert Guide		Free text	Enabling FAIR Data – FAQs	
4	Abstract / Description	A brief synopsis about or description of the learning resource.	TEXT (2000)	Free text	This module is a guide designed by European experts to help social science researchers make their research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR).		Free text	This FAQ is a companion to the Enabling FAIR Data Commitment Statement and the Author Guidelines being implemented by publishers who are signatories. ("FAIR" is defined as findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable in the FAIR Guiding Principles.) This FAQ is not meant to contradict anything stated in either the Commitment Statement or the Author Guidelines. Instead, it is meant to help provide answers to common questions.	
5	Author(s)	Name of entity(ies) authoring the resource.	TEXT	Multiple authors should be listed with commas between the names. Names should include given or first name and family or surname, and a personal identifier such as an ORCID, if available.	CESSDA Training Working Group		Multiple authors should be listed with commas between the names. Names should include given or first name and family or surname, and a personal identifier such as an ORCID, if available.	The Coalition for Publishing Data in the Earth and Space Sciences (COPDESS)	
6	Primary Language	Language in which the resource was originally published or made available.	TEXT (2)	String composed by a code as defined by the code set ISO 639-1:2002	en		String composed by a code as defined by the code set ISO 639-1:2002	en	
7	Keyword(s)	Keywords or tags used to describe the resource.	TEXT (100)	Free text or keywords from a given vocabulary	data management process plan archive discover store publish	repeatable singular value	Free text or keywords from a given vocabulary	fair data fairness faq	repeatable singular value

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8	License	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL	TEXT (100); should be available for URL as well; specify in application profile	Free text or keywords from a given vocabulary	Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License		Free text or keywords from a given vocabulary, e.g., the NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS), http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L08/current/	Not available	
9	Version Date	Version date for the most recently published or broadcast resource.	DATE	Format: YYYY-MM-DD IETF RFC3339 ISO 8601 OR another format or not available	2017-2019		Format: YYYY-MM-DD IETF RFC3339 ISO 8601 OR another format or not available	Not available	
10	URL to Resource	URL that resolves to the learning resource or to a "landing page" for the resource that contains important contextual information including the direct resolvable link to the resource, if applicable. Should be a PID, if possible. Controlled vocabulary	TEXT (1000)	Free text	https://www.cessda.eu/Training/Training-Resources/Library/Data-Management-Expert-Guide		Free text	http://www.copdess.org/enabling-fair-data-project/enabling-fair-data-faqs/	
11	Resource URL Type	designating the persistent identifier schemes used for the resource, e.g., DOI, ARK, Handle.	TEXT (1000)	Codelist from a CV including values like URL, ARK, DOI, etc.	URL		Codelist from a CV including values like URL, ARK, DOI, etc.	URL	
12	Target Group (Audience) (row 32)	Principle users(s) for which the resource was designed.	TEXT (40)	Codelist from a recommended CV or personalised text if not available in the list	Social science researchers		Codelist from a recommended CV or personalised text if not available in the list	General public	

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13	Learning Resource Type (row 31)	The predominant type or kind that characterizes the learning resource.	TEXT (40)	<p>Codelist from a CV including values like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - exercise - simulation - questionnaire - diagram - figure - graph - index - slide - table - narrative text - exam - experiment - problem statement - self assessment - lecture 	Narrative text		<p>Codelist from a CV including values like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - exercise - simulation - questionnaire - diagram - figure - graph - index - slide - table - narrative text - exam - experiment - problem statement - self assessment - lecture <p>Or the possibility to select "other --> FAQ"</p>	FAQ	
14	Learning Outcome(s) (See RDA_row 46)	Descriptions of what knowledge, skills or abilities students should acquire on completion of the resource.	TEXT (1000)	Free text	Learners will be guided by different European experts who are - on a daily basis - busy ensuring long-term access to valuable social science datasets, available for discovery and reuse at one of the CESSDA social science data archives.		Free text	This FAQ is meant to help provide answers to common questions.	

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15	Access Cost; see RDA_row5	Access cost: Choice stating whether or not there is a fee for use of the resource (CV = Y/N/Maybe with recommendation that further explanation of "Maybe" goes in the Description field for "It depends" or "It changes" explanations).	TEXT (8)	Codelist with values like Yes, No, Maybe OR Codelist associated with a CV with values like open access; embargoed access; restricted access; metadata only access	No		Codelist with values like Yes, No, Maybe OR Codelist associated with a CV with values like open access; embargoed access; restricted access; metadata only access	Open access	
16	Expertise Level (Skill level);	Target skill level in the topic being taught; example values include: beginner, intermediate,	TEXT	Codelist with values like beginner, intermediate, advanced	Beginner		Codelist with values like beginner, intermediate, advanced	Beginner	
17									
18									